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Formalization and the Corporate Governance of Family-Owned Businesses in the South-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined formalization and the corporate governance of family-owned businesses in South-East, Nigeria. Descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection was adopted. Data was obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was gathered through questionnaire while the secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related family businesses. The study population consisted of 43,868 family-owned businesses. The sample size is 554 determined using Cochran (1963) statistical formula. Analyses were carried out using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level while a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) alpha level. All analyses were carried out in SPSS 20.0.

Keywords: Formalization, Corporate Governance, Family-Owned Businesses and Sustainability

Introduction: The term 'formalization' includes rules and regulations, policies, methods and activities of an organization in written form (Price and Mueller, 1986; Danish, Ramzan and Ahmad, 2015). It also refers to the rules, procedures, and written documents based on which the tasks, instructions, and commands are described for the staff of an organization (Hassan and Mojtaba, 2016). Formalization according to Adler and Borys (1996) helps to enhance the motivation level in employees and made them more efficient. Formalization can decrease the commitment employee satisfaction (Organ and Greene, 1982; Walton, 1985; Danish, Ramzan and Ahmad, 2015) and it can as well increase the same (Greene, 1978; Morris and Steers, 1980; Jermier, 1982; and Danish, Ramzan and Ahmad, 2015). Nevertheless, the main thrust of this study was to examine the effect of formalization on the corporate governance of family-owned businesses. To achieve the research objective, one research question was formulated for the study which sought to determine the extent to which formalization affects the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. One hypothesis was formulated in line with the objective of the study and research question that formalization significantly affects the corporate governance in family-owned businesses in South-East, Nigeria.

This study will be anchored on two theories: the agency theory and the resource dependency theory. The agency theory is chosen since it can help us to understand better the employees and management as well as their relationship with the owners. On the hand, resource dependency theory helps to explain the way Boards facilitates access to key resources (human capital and finance) thereby contributing to the company's value creation.

Demir (2008) examined the effect of formalization on role stress, job dissatisfaction, organisational commitment, and alienation, and the possible effect of the moderating variables such as job tenure, age, and higher order need strength within a group of teachers. Interrelationships of organizational formalization and work outcomes were also analysed with the data obtained from 256 primary and secondary school teachers. The study found formalization to decrease both types of role stresses and increases organizational commitment.

Similarly, Danish, Sidra & Ahmad (2015) examined the effect of formalization on organizational commitment in the service sector of Lahore, Pakistan. The study analyzed the interactional role of self-monitoring in the relationship between formalization and organizational commitment. Data was collected from the employees working in different hotels, hospitals, financial and educational institutions in the service sector which covers both the private and public sectors. Convenience sampling was used for data collection. Almost 680 questionnaires were distributed whereas useable questionnaires for further analysis are 355. Structural equation modelling and regression analysis were used to determine the results. The study found that formalization was positively and significantly related to effective, continuance and normative commitment. The study also found that self-monitoring moderates the relationship between formalization and organizational commitment. The study concludes that the formalized procedures, rules and regulations increase the organizational commitment whereas, self-monitoring further helps to moderates this relationship in employees of the service sector. The study recommends that organizations should retain their employees by providing formalized rules, regulations, procedures and different activities of an organization as well as provide proper training to their employees about personality characteristics such as self-monitoring.

Another study conducted by Yasser (2011) examined the challenges in corporate governance in a family-controlled business perspective and described the importance of corporate governance in family owned business and challenges facing these businesses in a new era. The study notes that organizations are especially susceptible to loss of vision and purpose during periods of CEO transition which underscores the need and importance of formalization given the fact that leaders who facilitated and shape the vision are replaced by others who may not share the same values and capabilities. The study notes that weaknesses in corporate governance structures of family businesses are most evident in internal controls, implementation of effective internal audit and realization of risk management. Since many family controlled businesses are managed by the founders or their children, with their close supervisor the control environment is largely customized to their needs and according to their indulgent. The problem comes when controls do not grow along with the company, as the businesses grow with the passage of time and situation becomes more complex. This space is a crucial spot of concern for external investors for their decision making and long-term survival.

Methodology: The design adopted for this study is a descriptive survey method based on primary and secondary sources of data collection. The data for this study was obtained from primary sources otherwise known as field survey and secondary sources otherwise called desk survey. Primary data was gathered through a structured questionnaire. The objective was to gather related, rich, detailed and specific information used in the analyses and to confirm, corroborate, dispute, reject or establish new facts or truth. The secondary data was gathered from a review of several research publications, annual reports, articles, textbooks, unpublished thesis, journals and internet sources related to organization structure and family businesses. The study population consist of registered and unregistered family-owned businesses in Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and the Imo States. A pilot study conducted by the researcher indicates there are about 43,868 family-owned businesses in the South-East. Cochran (1963) statistical formula was used to determine the sample size that gives 554. To ensure that the sample size determined above truly represent each State, a stratified random sampling technique was adopted using Bowley's proportional allocation statistical technique. The survey instrument was developed on the basis of information required to examine the research objectives of the study and composed of structured

questionnaire divided into two parts namely Part A and Part B. Part A provides general information about the respondents while Part B focuses on the research questions broken into item questions to elicit responses from the respondents about their businesses. Likert scale grading format was used in designing the questionnaire. To ascertain the validity of the research instrument, the researcher subjected the instrument to face, construct, contents and response validations. To test the reliability of the research instrument, a pilot study was carried out to ensure that the items in the questionnaire were stated in clear terms without ambiguity with the same meaning to all the respondents. In order to measure internal consistency, Spearman' Rank Correlation Coefficient (r) was used to test the reliability of responses by the 25 respondents. The result shows that the Cronbach's Alpha of $0.84 > 0.70$ was achieved. This implies that the reliability of the test instrument was very high and reliable too. The study analyses made using simple descriptive statistics organized and presented in tables, frequency and simple percentages to calculate, analyse, show and summarize responses of the respondents and the research question in a meaningful way. At the inferential level of statistical analyses, the hypothesis was subjected to double-test using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to determine their statistical significance or otherwise. To establish whether an outcome is statistically significant, the researcher set up a 5% significance level. This implies that the researcher accepted a statistical significance occurring 5 times out of 100 (5/100) by chance. Thus, a 95% confidence level was applied and tested at 5% ($p\text{-value} \leq 0.05$) alpha level. The maximum acceptable risk of making type 1 error (rejecting the null hypotheses (H_0) when it should have been accepted) is 5%. Hence, the decision rule adopted in this study is to reject the null hypotheses where the calculated p-value at 5% significance level with the respective degrees of freedom is greater than the critical or table value, otherwise, the null hypotheses should be accepted. However, using the probability value (p-value) produced from the SPSS software, the decision rule was to reject the null hypotheses if the probability value was less than the chosen 5% alpha level otherwise, accepted.

Data Presentation

Table 1: Administration and Return of Questionnaire

	Returned (R)	536	96.8	96.8	96.8
Valid	Not Returned (NR)	18	3.2	3.2	100.0
	Total	554	100.0	100.0	

Source: Data Analyses in IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 1 above shows that a total of five hundred and fifty-four (554) questionnaire was printed and administered to the respondents by the researcher. The breakdown shows that five hundred and thirty-six (536) representing a response rate of 96.8% were returned while eighteen (18) questionnaire representing a non-response rate of 3.2% were not returned.

Table 2: Abia State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Returned (R)	137	95.1	95.1	95.1	
Valid	Not Returned (NR)	6	4.2	4.2	99.3
	Not Properly Filled	1	.7	.7	100.0
	Total	144	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 2 above shows a total of one hundred and forty-four (144) questionnaire distributed to respondents in Abia State, South-East, Nigeria. The table also shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected. A look at the table shows that one hundred and thirty-eight (138) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and forty-four (144) distributed. This represents a 96.7% response rate. It further shows that one

hundred and thirty-seven (137) were adjudged good for analyses representing 95.1%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.7% while six (6) questionnaire was not returned representing 4.2%.

Table 3: Anambra State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	126	96.9	96.9	96.9
Not Returned (NR)	3	2.3	2.3	99.2
Not Properly Filled	1	.8	.8	100.0
Total	130	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 3 above shows that a total of one hundred and thirty (130) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Anambra State, South-East, Nigeria. It shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected. A look at the table shows that one hundred and twenty-seven (127) questionnaire were returned out of one hundred and thirty (130) distributed. This represents a 98.6% response rate. A further breakdown shows that one hundred and twenty-six (126) were adjudged good for analyses representing 96.9%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 0.8% while two (2) questionnaire was not returned representing 2.3%.

Table 4: Ebonyi State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	93	98.9	98.9	98.9
Not Returned (NR)	1	1.1	1.1	100.0
Total	94	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version

The table 4 above shows that a total of ninety-four (94) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Ebonyi State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table above shows the breakdown of the questionnaire distributed and collected in Ebonyi State. The table shows that all the ninety-four (94) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents 100.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-three (93) was adjudged good for analyses representing 98.9% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.1%.

Table 5: Enugu State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned (R)	83	97.6	97.6	97.6
Not Returned (NR)	1	1.2	1.2	98.8
Not Properly Filled	1	1.2	1.2	100.0
Total	85	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 4.5 above shows that a total of eighty-five (85) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Enugu State, South-East, Nigeria. The table equally shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected in Enugu State. It shows that eighty-four (84) out of eighty-five (85) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 99.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that eighty-three (83) were adjudged good for analyses representing 97.6%, one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% and one questionnaire was not properly filled representing 1.2% respectively.

Table 6: Imo State Questionnaire Administration and Return

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Returned ®	97	96.0	96.0	96.0
Valid Not Returned (NR)	2	2.0	2.0	98.0
Not Properly Filled	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
Total	101	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 6 above shows that a total of one hundred and one (101) questionnaire were distributed to respondents in Imo State, South-East, Nigeria. A look at the table above shows the breakdown of a questionnaire distributed and collected in Imo State. The table shows that the ninety-nine (99) questionnaire distributed were returned. This represents a 98.0% response rate. A further breakdown shows that ninety-seven (97) was adjudged good for analyses representing 96.0% and two questionnaires were not properly filled representing 2.0% while another two were not returned representing 2.0% respectively.

Analyses of Research Objective

How does formalization affect the corporate governance of family-owned businesses?

Coded responses on: To what extent does formalization affects the corporate governance in family-owned businesses?

Table 7: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness	533	3.874	1.0392
Corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations	533	4.276	.9404
Formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners	533	4.054	1.1580
Lack of formalization in family-owned businesses hinders growth, good corporate governance and sustainability	533	3.520	1.3566
Good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses	533	1.694	.8855
Valid N (listwise)	533		

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

The table 7 above shows the mean score of each item question in the research question four. A calculation of the all the mean shows a grand total of 17.418 in all. A further breakdown shows a grand mean score of 3.4836. Thus, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.4836 as calculated from the descriptive table above indicate that formalization has a significant effect on the corporate governance in family-owned businesses.

Table 8: Formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	20	3.8	3.8	3.8
Disagree	33	6.2	6.2	9.9
Undecided	106	19.9	19.9	29.8
Agree	209	39.2	39.2	69.0

Strongly Agree	165	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 8 above present results of responses of item question one in research question four that seeks to examine the extent to which formalization affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is twenty (20) representing 3.8%, thirty-three (33) respondents of disagreeing represent 6.2% and one hundred and six (106) of undecided representing 19.9%. However, two hundred and nine (209) respondents agree to represent 39.2% and one hundred and sixty-five (165) respondents strongly agree to represent 31.0%. This implies that 10.0% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness. Similarly, 70.2% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness while 19.9% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.874 as shown in the descriptive table above indicates that formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness.

Table 9: Corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct and profitable entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly Disagree	15	2.8	2.8	2.8
Disagree	29	5.4	5.4	8.3
Undecided	5	.9	.9	9.2
Agree	229	43.0	43.0	52.2
Strongly Agree	255	47.8	47.8	100.0
Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 9 above present results of responses of item question two in research question four that seeks to examine the extent to which formalization affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is fifteen (15) representing 2.8%, twenty-nine (29) respondents of disagreeing represent 5.4% and five (5) of undecided representing 0.9%. However, two hundred and twenty-nine (229) respondents agree to represent 43.0% and two hundred and fifty-five (255) respondents strongly agree to represent 47.8%. This implies that 8.2% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct and profitable entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations. Similarly, 90.8% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct and profitable entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations while 0.9% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.276 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct and profitable entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations.

Table 10: Formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly Disagree	32	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Disagree	46	8.6	8.6	14.6
	Undecided	13	2.4	2.4	17.1
	Agree	212	39.8	39.8	56.8
	Strongly Agree	230	43.2	43.2	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 10 above present results of responses of item question three in research question four that seeks to examine the extent to which formalization affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is thirty-two (32) representing 6.0%, forty-six (46) respondents of disagreeing represent 8.6% and thirteen (13) of undecided representing 2.4%. However, two hundred and twelve (212) respondents agree to represent 39.8% and two hundred and thirty (230) respondents strongly agree to represent 43.2%. This implies that 14.6% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners. Similarly, 83.0% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners while 2.4% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 4.054 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners.

Table 11: Lack of formalization in family-owned businesses hinders growth, good corporate governance and sustainability

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly Disagree	68	12.8	12.8	12.8
	Disagree	77	14.4	14.4	27.2
	Undecided	40	7.5	7.5	34.7
	Agree	206	38.6	38.6	73.4
	Strongly Agree	142	26.6	26.6	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0	

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 11 above present results of responses of item question four in research question four that seeks to examine the extent to which formalization affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is sixty-eight (68) representing 12.8%, seventy-seven (77) respondents of disagreeing represent 14.4% and forty (40) of undecided representing 7.5%. However, two hundred and six (206) respondents agree to represent 38.6% and one hundred and forty-two (142) respondents strongly agree to represent 26.6%. This implies that 27.2% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that lack of formalization in family-owned businesses hinders growth, good corporate governance and sustainability. Similarly, 65.2% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that lack of formalization in family-owned businesses hinders growth, good corporate governance and sustainability while 7.5% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 3.520 as shown in the descriptive

table presented earlier indicates that formalization is needed in family-owned businesses to ensure growth, good corporate governance and sustainability.

Table 12: Good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	266	49.9	49.9
	Disagree	204	38.3	88.2
	Undecided	32	6.0	94.2
	Agree	22	4.1	98.3
	Strongly Agree	9	1.7	100.0
	Total	533	100.0	100.0

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 12 above present results of responses of item question five in research question four that seeks to examine the extent to which formalization affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses based on the responses of the respondents shows a response frequency of five hundred and thirty-three (533). The observed response rate of strongly disagree is two hundred and sixty-six (266) representing 49.9%, two hundred and four (204) respondents of disagreeing represent 38.3% and thirty-two (32) of undecided representing 6.0%. However, twenty-two (22) respondents agree to represent 4.1% and nine (9) respondents strongly agree to represent 1.7%. This implies that 88.2% of the respondents disagree/strongly disagree that good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses. Similarly, 5.8% of the respondents agree/strongly agree that good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses while 6.0% were indifferent. Therefore, given that the acceptance point is 3.0, the grand mean value of 1.694 less than 3.0 as shown in the descriptive table presented earlier indicates that respondents reject that good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses. Therefore, good corporate governance from the analysis is a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses

Test of Hypothesis

H₀: Formalization does not affect the corporate governance in family-owned businesses

H₁: Formalization significantly affects the corporate governance in family-owned businesses

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Formalization of family-owned businesses	4.054	1.1580	533
Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses	1.683	.4658	533

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 14: Correlations

		Formalization of family-owned businesses	Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses
Formalization of family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	1	.733**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	533	533
Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses	Pearson Correlation	.733**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	

N	533	533
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** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 15: Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.733 ^a	.537	.536	.3174	.537	614.839	1	531	.000	.025

a. Predictors: (Constant), Formalization of family-owned businesses

b. Dependent Variable: Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 16: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	61.930	1	61.930	614.839	.000 ^b
Residual	53.485	531	.101		
Total	115.415	532			

a. Dependent Variable: Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses

b. Predictors: (Constant), Formalization of family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

Table 17: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	.488	.050		9.748	.000	.390	.587
	Formalization of family-owned businesses	.295	.012	.733	24.796	.000	.271	.318

a. Dependent Variable: Good corporate governance in family-owned businesses

Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20.0 Version.

R = 0.733

R² = 0.537

F = 614.839

T = 9.748

DW = 0.025

Interpretation and Decision: Table 13 shows the descriptive statistics of the relationship between formalization and good corporate governance in family-owned businesses. Formalization has a mean score of 4.054 and standard deviation of 1.1580 while good corporate governance has a mean score of 1.683 and a standard deviation of 0.4658. A careful observation of the standard deviation values reveals that the variability of data points amongst the dependent and the independent variables. However, the implication of the result is that formalization constitutes a greater percentage of variables that significantly affect corporate governance in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. In table 4.3.8d, the regression sum of squares (61.930) is greater than the residual sum of squares (53.485) which indicate that more of the variation in the dependent variable is not explained by the model. The significance value of the F statistic (0.00) is less than 0.05 which means that the variation explained by the model is not due to chance.

R, the correlation coefficient which has a value of 0.733 indicate that there is a positive and significant relationship between formalization and corporate governance in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria. R square, the coefficient of determination shows that 53.7% of the variation in the corporate governance of family-owned businesses is explained by the model. With the linear regression model, the error of the estimated value of 0.3174 is low. The Durbin Watson statistic of 0.025 which is less than 2 indicates that there is no autocorrelation.

The influence of formalization on the corporate governance in family-owned businesses coefficient of 0.733 indicates a significant and positive relationship between formalization and corporate governance which is statistically significant with $t = 9.748$. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted. Therefore, we conclude based on the results above that formalization positively and significantly affects corporate governance in family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The study sought to determine the effect of formalization on the corporate governance of family-owned businesses. The result of the analyses of research question four as earlier presented revealed that formalization significantly affected the corporate governance of family-owned businesses. The computed mean of the observed responses was 3.5 higher than the expected mean of 3.00 suggests that formalization positively and significantly affected the corporate governance of family-owned businesses. The hypothesis of the study was equally subjected to double test using both Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient and Simple Linear Regression to determine the effect of formalization on the corporate governance of family-owned businesses led to the rejection of null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternate hypothesis. Thus, the study concludes that there is a correlation between formalization and corporate governance which is further confirmed with another test statistic that shows the positive and significant effect of formalization on the corporate governance of family-owned businesses in the South-East, Nigeria ($r = 0.733$, $t = 9.748$, $F = 614.839$ $p < 0.05$).

The above finding agrees with the study carried out by Malik (2017) in a study titled ‘Organizational Structure and Employee’s Performance: A Study of Brewing Firms in Nigeria’ found that formalization significantly affects employee’s performance positively. The present findings also agree with Danish, Ramzan and Ahmad (2015) that formalization is positively and significantly related to effective, continuance and organizational commitment. Formalization according to Adler and Borys (1996) also helps to enhance the motivation level of employees and made them more efficient. Other related studies in agreement with the findings are Morris and Steers (1980), Jermier (1982), and Greene (1978) who found a positive association between formalization and organizational commitment of their employees. Khan, Lieb and Meiren (2018) also found a positive and significant relationship between formalized New Service Development process and performance in German and Swiss firms.

Summary of Findings: This study made the following findings:

- i. That formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness.
- ii. That corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct and profitable entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations.
- iii. That formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners.
- iv. That formalization is needed in family-owned businesses to ensure growth, good corporate governance and sustainability
- v. That good corporate governance is a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses.

Conclusion and Recommendation: The study concludes based on the results above that formalization has a significant effect on the corporate governance in family-owned businesses.

The study recommends that for the family-owned businesses to make appreciable progress in the light of ever-changing business environment, formalization and good corporate governance is a necessity.

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APPENDIX

Questionnaire

Instruction: The options to select are in the following scale. Please, indicate your opinion by shading below the number which matches your opinion in the table below:

5 = Strongly Agree (SA)

4 = Agree (A)

3 = Undecided (U)

2 = Disagree (D)

1 = Strongly Disagree (SD)

To determine the influence of formalization on the corporate governance in family-owned businesses					
Questions	SA	A	U	D	SD
a. Formalization in family-owned businesses allows for experienced, qualified and desired technical competence to be injected into the business which can promote sustainability and competitiveness					
b. Corporate governance in family-owned businesses allows business to be organized as a distinct entity which ensures smooth and sustained operations					
c. Formalization of family-owned businesses brings with it many gains such as access to funds, technical assistance and knowledge sharing with corporate entities which promote sustainability in the business and their owners					
d. Lack of formalization in family-owned businesses hinders growth, good corporate governance and sustainability					
e. Good corporate governance is not a condition for survival, growth, competitiveness and sustainability in family-owned businesses					